

DIDACTIC HERITAGE IN THE CREATION OF ABDULLA AVLONI

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Didactics recognizes education as a means of providing social experience. Abdullah Avloni relies on experience in this regard. Indeed, reading is an integral part of the educational process. From a psychological point of view, there is no doubt that this approach is a priority. However, from the point of view of pedagogical, ie social experience, teaching, the main relationship for the activity is the relationship between two people, that is, the relationship between the student and the teacher. it is understood that it is necessary.

The success of the educational process depends not only on its formation, but also on the effectiveness of the methods used, which occupies one of the key positions in the theory of education. "Method" is derived from the Greek word "metodos" - "way", which means research. The teaching method is a collaborative process in which the teacher and students work together towards a specific goal in the learning process. Teaching methods are the ways to achieve the goals of teaching, as well as the theoretical and practical orientation of the teaching material.

In the process of analyzing his didactics, we became convinced that Abdullah Avloni also used effective methods of speech development in students using teaching methods.

It is well known that the main task of literature lessons is to teach students to read expressively in order to improve their speech. The events of a particular work, which serve as an educational tool, are embodied in the reader's eyes through expressive reading. The idea of the work is fully explained. The more Abdullah Avloni focused on literacy, the more attention he paid to understanding, reading, and feeling the work of art. During the lessons, he provided students with choir reading and exercises. Avloni himself was a conductor during the class. Because Avloni was also aware of the art of conducting. There are many forms of expressive reading, one of which is recitation. Declamation (Latin: declamatio) is one of the most important forms of public speaking in the East. Declamation masters worked in the palaces of Chinese, Indian kings, Khorezmshahs, Sugd, Sak khans. In the territory of the Uzbek khanates also lived and worked masters of this art, in particular, storytellers, storytellers, storytellers and horsemen. Poetry, which is often held in palaces, is in fact a form of recitation.

In the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries, the concept of declamation in Western classical theater generalized the means of acting. The declamatory form of expressive reading is inextricably linked to students' live speech. Abdullah Avloni's expressive reading lessons at school have become very popular in the field. On February 27, 1914, the Colosseum Theater in Tashkent was packed with more than 2,000 spectators. The first performance of Behbudi's drama "Padarkush". The play was connected with literary reading. Abdullah Avloni's students recited the poems "Family Discussion" and "Invitation to School", which were accompanied by a call to science and enlightenment in harmony with the drama "Padarkush", and were greeted with great applause by the audience.

Avloni, while organizing expressive reading lessons, described these lessons as a form of aesthetic education. In such classes, the student's speech develops and his love for the art of speech is awakened. In the process of learning, the student becomes not only a listener, but also a participant in the learning process. Abdullah Avloni is one of the first teachers in Turkestan to use technology in his teaching.

From 1910 to 1911, representatives of the Grammafong Company in Riga came to the cities of Central Asia and recorded on the record the classical status and songs of the famous hafiz among the Uzbek, Kazakh, Tajik and Kyrgyz peoples. Abdullah Avloni used the gramophone to teach the people in order to educate them. He taught his students to recite some of the poems in the Literature or National Poems textbook. In his Avloni textbooks, he mainly followed the principle of comprehensibility. He stressed the importance of school textbooks for the education of children, as well as the role of teachers.

The main task of education is to equip the individual with scientific knowledge, skills and abilities. Education, as a type of human cognitive activity, has several meanings, namely, the formation of knowledge, skills and abilities in learners, the formation of their worldview, thoughts and beliefs, and the development of their abilities.

Abdullah Avloni's teachings also focus on strengthening the youth and keeping them physically healthy. In physical education, Abdullah Avloni appeals first to himself and then to his parents in raising a healthy child. The teacher appreciates the work of the child in the intellectual upbringing. Human health is not enhanced by itself, but by human activity. A person without good health cannot perform the tasks assigned to him. Abdullah Avloni also gives valuable advice on how to make young people physically strong, fearless and courageous.

In the "Brave" chapter of "Turkish Gulistan or Morality" he thought about the courageous upbringing of children. It is also important for young people to grow up healthy.

"A man of courage will have a courage and a heart that is not afraid of anything. Courage should not be lost in any endeavor. Courage is the pure mirror of man, the light of virtues such as chastity, zeal, perseverance." says Abdullah Avloni. A distinctive feature of Abdullah Avloni's didactics is that it is important in that it combines Eastern and Western literature. These textbooks have been adapted to the child's language in an understandable and interesting way.

The textbook, which is exemplary and educational in the child's mind and polished with educational and developmental texts and poems, is a vivid expression of Avloni's didactic views.

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor JG Yuldashev in his scientific article: "Abdullah Avloni used to examine his students once a year in the presence of parents, community members and others, openly demonstrating their academic achievements. they were amazed to see and hear with their own eyes the expression of their profound knowledge. "because he enriched the minds of children with meaningful educational and pedagogical ideas in his textbooks, which caused a great stir in his time. He also learned from him. that children's literacy was higher than that of children in other schools had attracted the attention of parents. " he writes.

Abdullah Avloni's work focuses on school, education and upbringing. In the course of studying the didactic teachings of Abdullah Avloni, it was concluded that he fully adhered to the principles of education. Avloni was the first Uzbek pedagogue to use technical means in teaching, and his work is reflected in scientific and historical sources.

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